

A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CROWN SPREAD VARIATION IN PTEROCARPUS MARSUPIUM AND P. SANTALINUS, ACROSS NORTH-SOUTH ASPECTS AND DIVERSE SEED SOURCES IN INDIA

V. B. Shambharkar^{1*}, M. B. Tandel², R. P. Gunaga³, S. K. Sinha⁴, V. B. Parekh⁵, Y.A. Garde⁶, H. K. Deshmukh⁷ and S. W. Choudhari⁸

¹Assistant Professor (Silviculture) College of Forestry, Dr.Panjabrao Deshmukh Krishi Vidyapeeth, Akola (MS)

:vbshambharkar@pdkv.ac.in

²Assistant Professor (Forestry) & IC Head (SAF), College of Forestry, NAU, Navsari (GJ), India.

³Associate Professor (FB/AF) & IC Head (FPU), College of Forestry, NAU, Navsari (GJ), India.

⁴Assistant Professor (WST), College of Forestry, NAU, Navsari (GJ)

⁵Assistant Professor (Forest Biotechnology), College of Forestry, NAU, Navsari (GJ), India

⁶Assistant Professor (Agricultural Statistics), College of Forestry, NAU, Navsari (GJ), India

⁷ & ⁸Assistant Professor, College of Forestry, Dr. PDKV, Akola (MS), India.

MS Received: 10.09.2024; MS Revised:16.09.2024; MS Accepted:17.09.2024)

MS 3285

(RESEARCH PAPER IN FORESTRY,)

Abstract

This study deals into the captivating phenomenon of diverse crown spreads along the north-south (CSNS) aspect within two distinct *Pterocarpus* species, namely *Pterocarpus marsupium* and *P. santalinus*. This investigation reveals distinct crown spread behaviors in these studied species, substantiated by rigorous analysis, adopting multistage sampling method. A comparative analysis between the two *Pterocarpus* species uncovers a significant interplay. Assessing the performance of each species in specific locations (GJ & MH and GJ & AP-TS), it was observed noteworthy variations in the CSNS aspect of both *P. marsupium* and *P. santalinus* between the two locations. Furthermore, when examining CSNS aspect variation between *P. marsupium* and *P. santalinus*, irrespective of their seed sources and locations, a substantial difference emerges. Specifically, *P. marsupium* exhibits a wider CSNS aspect (14.01 m), contrasting with the narrower CSNS aspect (9.79 m) observed in *P. santalinus*, which ranges from 7.80 m to 22.65 m and higher range 5.30 m to 24.00 m, respectively. These findings not only contribute valuable detailed into the elaborate dynamics of crown spread variation within *Pterocarpus* species but also hold implication to contribute species identification traits, and biodiversity conservation efforts, emphasizing the need for customized strategies considering the unique characteristics and behaviors exhibited by each species.

Key words : aspect, CSNS, locations, *Pterocarpus marsupium*, *P. santalinus*, seed sources

Introduction

The genus *Pterocarpus* belongs to the subfamily Papilionoideae of the Fabaceae family, within the order Leguminosae (Gupta, 1969). It comprises several species, including *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb. (Bijasal), *P. santalinus* Linn. (Raktachandan), *P. dalbergioides* Roxb., *P. macrocarpus* Kurz, and *P. indicus* Wild (Troup, 1921). This genus is of significant interest to foresters due to its valuable tree species, characterized by distinctive winged, one-seeded fruits. However, there is confusion in identification of particular species due to similar characteristics and especially presence of red fluid, and also having conflicting information regarding the exact number of species within the genus. While estimates range from 15 to 70 species (Allen and Allen, 1981; Hooker, 1879; Brandis, 1907), five species are recorded in India (Gamble, 1922; Troup, 1921; Pearson and Brown, 1932; Anon., 1962), and three are listed in Myanmar (Hundley and Chit, 1987). Several species within *Pterocarpus*, particularly rosewoods, are highly prized for their dark red, high-grade heartwood, which has significant economic value in industries such as fine furniture, traditional medicine, and handicrafts like musical instruments. Due to overexploitation and slow growth rates, some species are now at risk of extinction (Waeber *et al.*, 2019). For example, *P. santalinus*, native to the southern Eastern Ghats of India, is classified as endangered by the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) (Anon., 2018; Ahmedullah, 2021). Meanwhile, *P. marsupium*, found in India and Sri Lanka, is considered a "near-threatened" species due to its valuable wood and bioactive compounds from its stem bark and heartwood. Given the conservation concerns and limited research on these species, particularly regarding their phenology, this study aims to compare the crown spread variation of *Pterocarpus marsupium* (in Gujarat and Maharashtra) and *P. santalinus* (in Gujarat and Andhra Pradesh-Telangana state). The study focuses on crown spread in north-south aspects and selected seed sources across India, seeking to clarify identification and provide understanding into sustainable management.

Material And Method

Study Area and Seed Sources: The study was carried out during 2021 and 2022 across two states in India: and survey was conducted purposefully for *Pterocarpus marsupium* in Gujarat (GJ) and Maharashtra, while Gujarat (GJ) and Andhra Pradesh-Telangana state (AP-TS) for *P. santalinus* species, these location (States) has rich sources of species in natural forest and in plantation, hence these regions were selected purposively based on resource availability. In each state, five sites were chosen as seed sources. The treatments (seed sources) were prepared as, for *Pterocarpus marsupium* seed sources from Gujarat as GJ-PM-1, GJ-PM-2, GJ-PM-3, GJ-PM-4, GJ-PM-5, whereas for Other state (Maharashtra) as OS-PM-1, OS-PM-2 OS-PM-3 OS-PM-4 OS-PM-5; and for *Pterocarpus santalinus* the seed sources from Gujarat were labeled as GJ-PS-1, GJ-PS-2, GJ-PS-3, GJ-PS-4, and GJ-PS-5, while the seed sources from Other state (Andhra Pradesh-Telangana) were labeled as OS-PS-1, OS-PS-2, OS-PS-3, OS-PS-4, and OS-PS-5 (Table-1).

Sampling Method: A multistage random sampling method was employed to select trees (5 trees from each seed sources) from five seed sources across the two states for each species that was for *Pterocarpus marsupium* species from Gujarat and Maharashtra, whereas *P. santalinus* from Gujarat and Andhra Pradesh-Telangana state. Data collection was carried out directly in the field.

Measurement of Crown Spread: The crown spread of the selected trees was measured using a measuring tape and expressed in meters. Measurements were taken in the north-south direction to account for the crown's maximum exposure to sunlight. The crown spread was recorded at the widest point across the tree horizontally.

Data Analysis: The collected data were processed and analyzed statistically. The results are presented in tabular form, and conclusions were drawn based on the statistical inferences.

Table 1: Treatment (Seed source) details for *Pterocarpus marsupium* and *P. santalinus*

Location No.	Seed source Code	Seed source	Location No.	Seed source Code	Seed source
<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i>			<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i>		
Gujarat (GJ) seed sources			Gujarat (GJ) seed sources		
1	GJ-PM-1	NAU Campus, Navsari, Gujarat	1	GJ-PS-1	Farmers Field, Vyara (Tapi), Gujarat

2	GJ-PM-2	Farmer's Field, Sunthwad, Gujarat	2	GJ-PS-2	Rajpipala Forest Garden, Plantation, Rajpipala
3	GJ-PM-3	Panas Medicinal Garden Khaparda, Gujarat	3	GJ-PS-3	Vishalkhadi Forest, Rajpipala Road, Gujarat
4	GJ-PM-4	Waghai Botanical Garden, Waghai, Gujarat	4	GJ-PS-4	Farmer's Field, Dhamdod, Bharuch, Gujarat
5	GJ-PM-5	Vishalkhadi Forest Range, Rajpipala Rd, Gujarat	5	GJ-PS-5	Farmers Field, Amblikhed, Godhra, Gujarat
Maharashtra (MH) seed sources			Andhra Pradesh & Telangana (AP-TS) seed sources		
6	OS-PM-1	Pindkepar Forest Range, Sakoli, Maharashtra	6	OS-PS-1	Telangana State Forest Academy, Dullapally, Telangana
7	OS-PM-2	Papala Khurd Forest Range, Sakoli, Maharashtra	7	OS-PS-2	Farmers Field, Cherlopalle, Andhra Pradesh
8	OS-PM-3	Bolde Forest Range, Sakoli, Maharashtra	8	OS-PS-3	Farmers Field, Tirupati Dist-Chittoor, Andhra Pradesh
9	OS-PM-4	Bortekadi Forest Range, Gondia, Maharashtra	9	OS-PS-4	Farmers Field, Kasamkuppam Chennai-Anantpur Rd, Andhra Pradesh
10	OS-PM-5	Kawatha-4, Pratapgad Forest Range, Gondia, Maharashtra	10	OS-PS-5	Farmers Field, Narsingapuram, Chadari Mandal, Chittoor, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh

Result And Discussion

The present study delves into the intriguing phenomenon of varying crown spreads in north-south (CSNS) aspect within two distinct species of *Pterocarpus*. Specifically, *Pterocarpus marsupium* and *P. santalinus* showed differential crown spread behaviors, an observation

substantiated by rigorous analysis. Comparative analysis between the two *Pterocarpus* species reveals significant interplay.

The data with respect to variation in crown spread in north-south aspect (CSNS) of two *Pterocarpus* species are presented in Table 2, 3 and 4 and graphically depicted in Figure 1 and 2.

Table 2: Variation in tree crown spread (N-S) of *Pterocarpus marsupium* and *P. santalinus* at different locations

Crown spread (N-S) (m)			
<i>P. marsupium</i>		<i>P. santalinus</i>	
Seed source		Seed source	
GJ		GJ	
GJ-PM-1	12.36 ^b	GJ-PS-1	7.63 ^b
GJ-PM-2	12.38 ^b	GJ-PS-2	7.50 ^b
GJ-PM-3	10.00 ^b	GJ-PS-3	7.78 ^b
GJ-PM-4	16.58 ^a	GJ-PS-4	6.32 ^b
GJ-PM-5	11.44 ^b	GJ-PS-5	10.84 ^a
S.Em. ±	1.64	S.Em. ±	0.73
C.D. at 5 %	3.42	C.D. at 5 %	1.51
C.V. %	20.64	C.V. %	14.30
MH		AP-TS	
OS-PM-1	14.04	OS-PS-1	5.93 ^d
OS-PM-2	14.44	OS-PS-2	6.78 ^{cd}
OS-PM-3	14.18	OS-PS-3	7.59 ^c
OS-PM-4	17.00	OS-PS-4	15.45 ^b
OS-PM-5	17.66	OS-PS-5	22.10 ^a
S.Em. ±	2.20	S.Em. ±	0.65
C.D. at 5 %	NS	C.D. at 5 %	1.36
C.V. %	22.53	C.V. %	8.90

Note: The mean values with the same letter are not significantly different

The data presented in Table 2, 3 and 4 revealed that, crown spread in north-south aspect of *P. marsupium* and *P. santalinus* from different seed sources varied significantly within GJ and GJ & AP-TS, however crown spread variation in north-south aspect of *P. marsupium* was found non-significant. However, considering the crown spread (N-S) variation of *Pterocarpus* spp. between two locations, both *P. marsupium* and *P. santalinus* showed significant variation between two locations (GJ & MH and GJ & AP-TS). When comparing crown spreads (N-S) variation between *P. marsupium* and *P. santalinus* irrespective of their seed sources and locations, it showed significant variation between two species.

Considering CSNS aspect variation of *P. marsupium* within GJ seed sources, the wider CSNS aspect was recorded in GJ-PM-4 (16.58 m) followed by GJ-PM-2 (12.38 m) while others were at par with it. There was no noticeable difference was observed when it came to the seed

sources from Maharashtra state. By comparing all seed sources of *P. marsupium* irrespective of its locations, the wider CSNS aspect was recorded in OS-PM-5 (17.66 m) followed by GJ-PM-4 (17.00 m) whereas the narrower CSNS aspect was registered in GJ-PM-3 (10.00 m) and GJ-PM-5 (11.44 m) (Table 2).

In case of variation of CSNS aspect of *P. santalinus* within GJ seed sources, the wider CSNS aspect was found in GJ-PS-5 (10.84 m) followed by GJ-PS-3 (7.78 m), and others were at par with it. While considering AP-TS seed sources of *P. santalinus*, the wider CSNS aspect was observed in OS-PS-5 (22.10 m) followed by OS-PS-4 (15.45 m) whereas the narrower CSNS aspect was recorded in OS-PS-1 (5.93 m). By comparing all *P. santalinus* seed sources, regardless of their locations, the wider CSNS aspect was noted in OS-PS-5 (22.10 m) followed by OS-PS-4 (15.45 m) and GJ-PS-5 (10.84 m) whereas

the narrower CSNS aspect was registered in OS-PS-1 (5.93 m) and GJ-PS-4 (6.32 m) (Table 2).

Fig. 1: Variation in crown spread (N-S) (m) of *P. marsupium* among different seed sources of two locations

Fig. 2: Variation in crown spread (N-S) (m) of *P. santalinus* among different seed sources of two locations

Table 3: Comparison of crown spread (N-S) (m) between *Pterocarpus marsupium* and *P. santalinus* at two locations

	<i>P. marsupium</i>		<i>P. santalinus</i>	
	GJ	MH	GJ	AP-TS
Mean (m)	12.55	15.46	8.01	11.57
t - test	-3.02		-2.64	
P(T< t)	0.004*		0.011*	

Note: * Two sample t-test assuming equal variance

When comparing each species performance respective to its locations (GJ & MH and GJ & AP-TS), the CSNS aspect of *P. marsupium* and *P. santalinus* both varied significantly between its two locations (Table 3). The CSNS aspect of *P. marsupium* was noted maximum in

Maharashtra state location (15.46 m) as compared to GJ location (12.55 m) whereas CSNS aspect of *P. santalinus* was recorded maximum in AP-TS (11.57 m) as compared to GJ (8.01 m).

Table 4: Comparison of crown spread (N-S) (m) between *Pterocarpus marsupium* and *P. santalinus*

	<i>P. marsupium</i>	<i>P. santalinus</i>
Range (m)	7.80 - 22.65	5.30 - 24.00
Mean (m)	14.01	9.79
t - test	4.78	
P(T< t)	0.000*	

Note: * Two sample t-test assuming equal variance

In case of CSNS aspect variation between *P. marsupium* and *P. santalinus* irrespective of their seed sources and locations, it was found that there was significant variation in CSNS aspect between two species with wider CSNS aspect (14.01 m) was observed in *P. marsupium* whereas narrower CSNS aspect (9.79 m) was found in *P.*

santalinus. The CSNS aspect of *P. marsupium* and *P. santalinus* varied from 7.80 m to 22.65 m and 5.30 m to 24.00 m, respectively (Table 4). *Pterocarpus marsupium* have broader crown spread (14.01 m) as compared to *P. santalinus* (9.79 m). Whereas, *P. santalinus* displayed a wider range in crown spread in north-south (CSNS) aspects compared to *P. marsupium*. The CSNS ranged from 5.30 m to 24.00 m

in *P. santalinus* and 7.80 m to 22.65 m in *P. marsupium*. This indicates that the branches of *P. santalinus* extend farther ranged horizontally in north-south aspects. These measurements suggested that *P. marsupium* has a relatively more compact crown in North-South aspect compared to *P. santalinus*. It is worth noting that both species have spreading branches, as described by Gopikumar *et al.* (2003) and Reddy (2018). *P. marsupium* had a highly spreading crown, while *P. santalinus* was described as having stout, crooked stems with ranged widely spreading branches. All reported findings within the *Pterocarpus* species or other species were similar and within the range value recorded during our study and it confirms our results in both *Pterocarpus* species.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study search through the fascinating phenomenon of crown spread variation along the north-south aspect in two distinct *Pterocarpus* species viz. *Pterocarpus marsupium* and *P. santalinus*. The variations at seed sources level, in *P. santalinus* seed sources of other state (OS) performed better as compared to GJ seed sources. OS-PS-5 (22.10 m) seed source performed good in relation to CSNS aspect. The variations at location level for each species, it was observed that both locations had significant impact and significantly maximum CSNS aspect (15.46 m) observed in *P. marsupium* of Maharashtra location, while in case of *P. santalinus*, significantly maximum CSNS aspect (11.57 m) was recorded in AP-TS location. However the variations at species level, significant variation was recorded in CSNS aspect between two species with ranged of 7.80 m to 22.65 m with CSNS aspect was higher (14.01 m) in *P. marsupium*, while wider range (5.30 m to 24.00 m) of CSNS aspect with mean value of 9.79 m was observed in *P. santalinus*. These findings underscore the complex dynamics of crown spread within these species, offering understanding the distinct characteristics in each species for better identification of species, and emphasize the need for modifying conservation strategies that account for their unique ecological behaviors and adaptive traits for selection in breeding programme.

Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to the authorities at NAU, Navsari (GJ), for granting permission and providing the necessary facilities to conduct this research. I am also thankful to the authorities of Dr. PDKV, Akola (MS), for giving opportunity to undergo Doctoral degree program. My appreciation extends to the State Forest Departments of Gujarat, Maharashtra, Andhra Pradesh and Telangana state for their support, and to the Bijasal and Raktachandan tree growers for sharing valuable information and providing samples. I am deeply grateful to my research guide and SAC members for their invaluable guidance in compiling and analyzing the data.

References

1. **Ahmedullah, M. (2021).** *P. santalinus*. The IUCN Red List of threatened Species. 2021: e.T32104A187622484. Retrieved from <https://dx.doi.org/10.2305/IUCN.UK.2021-RLTS.T32104A187622484.en>.
2. **Allen, O.N. and Allen, E.K. (1981).** “*The Leguminosae – A Source Book of Characteristics, uses and Nodulation*”. Macmuan Publ. Ltd, London and Basingstoke, UK.
3. **Anonymous (1962).** “*A Dictionary of India Raw Materials and Industrial Products*”. Vol. VI (L-M), CSIR, Govt. of India Press, New Delhi.
4. **Anonymous (2018).** The IUCN red list of threatened species. Version 2016.2. In: *CAMP workshops on medicinal plants, India (January 1997) 1998, P. santalinus*. Retrieved from <http://www.iucnredlist.org/details/32104/0>.
5. **Arunkumar, A.N. (2011).** Variability studies in *P. santalinus* in different aged plantations of Karnataka. *My Forest*, 47(4):343-353.

6. **Brandis, D. (1907).** “*Indian Trees*”. Archibald Constable & Co., Ltd. London.
7. **Das, L.T. and Dayanand, T. (1984).** Some distinguishing characteristics between wavy-grained and straight-grained trees of Red Sanders (*P. santalinus*). *Indian J. Forestry*, 7(1): 69-71.
8. **Divakara, B.N. and Nikhitha, C.U. (2019).** Silviculture of *P. santalinus*. In: “*Red Sanders: Silviculture and Conservation*”, (Pullaiah, T.; Balasubramanya, S. and Anuradha, M. Ed.). Springer, Nature Singapore, Pvt. Ltd. pp. 101-124. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.4038/tare.v11i0.1786>.
9. **Gamble, J. S. (1922).** “*A Manual of Indian Timbers*”. (Sec. Ed.). Sampson Low, Marston and India Ltd., London.
10. **Gamble, J.S. (1902).** “*A manual of Indian timbers: an account of the growth, distribution and uses of the trees and shrubs of India and Ceylon, with descriptions of their wood structure*”. Simpson, Low, Marston & Co. Ltd, London.
11. **Gopikumar, K., Gopakumar, S. and Anoop, E.V. (2003).** “*Forest Nursery and Tree Husbandary*”. International Book Distributors, Dehradun, 170p.
12. **Gupta, B.L. (1969).** “*Forest flora of the Chakarta Dehradun and Baharanpur forest division, Uttar Pradesh*”. SFD, Dehradun; Vol.3.
13. **Gupta, S. and Uniyal, B.M. (2003).** Indian woods – their medicinal importance and identification. *Indian Forester* 129: 1225–1240.
14. **Hooker, J. D. (1879).** “*Flora of British India*” Vol.I, II & III. L. Reeve & Company, London.
15. **Hundley, H.G. and Chit K.K. (1987).** “*List of trees, shrubs, herbs and principal climbers of Burma*” (Fourth edn). Govt. Printing Press, Yangon.
16. **Kumar, R.S.; Nautiyal, P.K. and Bahuguna, Anjali (2004).** Seed source variation in Khair (*Acacia catechu*) Wild. *Indian J. For.*, pp.159-163.
17. **Padmalatha, K. and Prasad, M.N.V. (2007).** Morphological and molecular diversity in *P. santalinus* L.f: An endemic and endangered medicinal plant. *Med. & Arom. Plant Sci. & Biotech.*, 1: 263-273.
18. **Pearson, R.S. and Brown, H.P. (1932).** “*Commercial Timbers of India*”. Vol. I & II. Govt. of India. Central Publ. Branch, Calcutta.
19. **Pratikshya Chalise (2021).** “*Bijaysal - A Monograph of P. marsupium in Nepal*”: In: Taxonomy. Government of Nepal Ministry of Forests and Environment Department of Plant Resources National Herbarium and Plant Laboratories Godawari, Lalitpur, Nepal. pp. 6-11.
20. **Reddy, V.K.N.; Pradeep Kumar, H.; Siddraju, C.M.; Gunga, R.P.; Madiwalar, S.L. and Patil, S.K. (2007).** Seed source variation for seed and seedling traits in *Pongamia pinnata* (L.) Pierre; An important biofuel yielding tree species. *My For.*, 43(1): 61-68.
21. **Sukhadiya, Madhuri; Dholariya, C.; Behera, L.K.; Mehta, A.A.; Huse, S.A. and Gunaga, R.P. (2019).** Indian kino tree (*P. marsupium* roxb.): Biography of excellent timber tree species. *MFP NEWS*, 4 XXIX (1): 1-8.
22. **Troup, R.S. (1921).** “*The silviculture of Indian trees, Vol.1: Dilleniaceae to Leguminosae (Papilionaceae)*”. Clarendon Press, Oxford.
23. **Troup, R.S. (1921).** “*The Silviculture of Indian Trees*” Vol. 2: (*Leguminosae to Verbanaceae*)”, Clarendon Press, Oxford.